

ACCESSIBILITY FOR DIS-ABILITY: EMPOWERING DIFFERENTLY ABLED WOMEN IN THE LABOR FORCE

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the challenges and opportunities faced by differently abled women when joining and succeeding in the workforce. Despite progress in workplace inclusivity, many still face double discrimination, unfair hiring practices, inaccessible workplaces, and social biases. Through a qualitative approach and semi-structured interviews with five differently abled women, the study highlights their resilience, contributions, and the barriers they encounter. The researchers introduced the JEN Empowerment and Wellness Initiative for Differently Abled Women (JENEWIDAW). This program focuses on job placement with inclusive employers, skills training to enhance job readiness, and awareness campaigns to promote workplace inclusivity. It also offers mental health support to help participants build confidence, overcome challenges, and prepare for career success and beyond. The findings underscore the importance of equal opportunities, necessary accommodations, and breaking stereotypes. JENEWIDAW aims to empower differently abled women by improving their access to job opportunities, enhancing their skills, and supporting their mental well-being. Success will be measured by job placements, workplace inclusivity, and participants' personal and professional growth.

Keywords: *Differently Abled Women, Employment, Inclusivity, Double Discrimination, JENEWIDAW.*

INTRODUCTION

“The world worries about disability more than disabled people do.”

By Warwick Davis

A disability could be seen in any mental or physical situation that made it difficult to carry out specific activities (activity restrictions) and engage in surroundings. The World Health Organization estimated that 1.3 billion humans, or 16% of the world's population, were thought to be severely disabled as of the present day. People who had disabilities were a diverse community, and their sexual orientation, gender identity, and culture all had an impact on their everyday lives. Persons with disabilities died earlier, had lower health, and faced challenges in daily life than others. Work plays a significant role in shaping our identity and providing satisfaction and challenges. It fostered social connections beyond family ties and contributed to a smooth transition into adulthood. However, PWDs have historically faced difficulties in accessing education and employment opportunities, hindering their social inclusion.

Despite improvements in gender equality, differently abled women still encountered significant obstacles in finding and succeeding in jobs. While fewer people with disabilities worked compared to those without disabilities, differently abled women were particularly affected. This lack of representation limited their ability to earn money and made it harder to create workplaces where everyone felt welcome. (International Labor Organization [ILO], 2018). In Asia, the employment rate for people with disabilities was 80% or higher. One approach to address this issue was employing social trading (a business for profit and social responsibility) to include people with disabilities in the economy (Medalla & Medalla, 2018).

The study "Accessibility for Dis-Ability: Empowering Differently Abled Women in the Labor Force" explored the specific challenges restricting differently abled from entering and achieving success in the workforce. By promoting inclusive work environments, the study wanted to establish equal opportunity and unlock the immense value of this limited potential ability. Data suggests this group's labor force participation rate is significantly lower (Thomas & Turnbull, 2017).

Research Questions

Central Question

This study aimed to explore barriers that differently abled women encountered in the labor force.

Corollary Questions

1. What particular barriers to access do differently abled women face in the workplace?

2. What support systems are available to assist differently abled women in overcoming these barriers and securing employment?
3. What new strategies can employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations apply to make work environments easier and safer for differently abled women?
4. What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?
5. Based on the results of the study, what output may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This qualitative study had been conducted with women in the labor force in Calamba, Laguna. It was the most populous city in Region 4-A. Calamba had 539,671 people as of the 2020 census, accounting for 15.96% of Laguna's total population and 3.33% of CALABARZON's. The researchers chose Calamba because it was ideal for community-based research goals. By researching Calamba, researchers could get significant insights into the unique issues that differently abled women confronted in their community. Semi-structured interview questionnaires were used to obtain the data during the first semester of the 2024 academic year. Five (5) differently abled women participated. Purposive and snowball sampling were used in the study to guarantee its validity.

Research Design and Sampling Method

Narrative analysis was one of the qualitative research approaches utilized in this study. According to Brannan et al. (2022), the purpose of qualitative research was to completely comprehend participants' experiences, attitudes, and behaviors to offer insights into issues that arose in the actual world. Additionally, Thuv (2021) stated that narrative analysis was an effective tool in qualitative research in the context of narrative study. Interpretation in the response called for an examination of the writing in the hope of understanding the meaning that the writing conveyed. It enabled people to talk and narrate incidents and experiences that were closest to them, express their views on some of the issues that had occurred, bring out their emotions and feelings during the events, and state what they saw or heard. Together, the researchers obtained relevant firsthand information on the issues, concerns, and successes of differently abled women in the group.

This study employed inductive narrative analysis to obtain information on varied life stories and experiences working with differently abled women. According to Dovetail Editorial Team (2023), readers could create stories using inductive narrative analysis. Cues that could be used in interpreting the flow included where the participants' stories started and stopped. All the narratives were expected to have a beginning, middle, and end, although they might not always be clearly stated. By gathering these women's stories, this research aimed to bring out their encounters and create space for growth and empowerment among working women living with disabilities.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the interview with the participants, the researchers secured consent from the five participants in the study. The researchers in the current study employed questionnaires, most of which were open-ended. In the case of interviews, the researcher accompanied the participant to another area of her preference, though it was primarily secluded.

A recording feature in the form of an audio-visual recorder was applied to capture their responses during the interviews. Moreover, the researchers wrote down the participant's responses and conducted a comparison during the interpretation of the interview. This made it easier for emergent themes and trends to be identified, whereas, in turn-taking models where one person spoke and others listened, it was tough to note down such ideas.

Instrument of the Study

In this study, this study used open-ended, semi-structured interview questions as the primary tool. These interviews gathered qualitative data from the participants and lasted 45 minutes to an hour. According to Read (2018), researchers typically allocated between 45 minutes and two hours for each interview to ensure they had enough time to interview participants effectively. Semi-structured interviews were exploratory discussions often utilized in social sciences for qualitative research initiatives or to obtain clinical information. While it commonly adopted the rules that were told before the interview and was focused on the main topic to offer a general structure, the partially structured interview also enabled discovery, with room to follow issue trends as the subject matter unfolded (Berler & Magaldi, 2020).

Building Rapport Questions

1. Good day, Ma'am. It's a pleasure to meet you. How are you feeling today? (*Magandang araw, Ma'am. Ikinagagalak kong makilala kayo. Kamusta po ang pakiramdam niyo ngayon?*)
2. Is there anything you'd like to share about your day so far? (*May gusto po ba kayong ibahagi tungkol sa inyong araw ngayon?*)
3. What are your expectations for this interview? (*Ano po ang inaasahan ninyo sa panayam na ito?*)
4. Before we begin, I just want to make sure you're comfortable and ready to proceed. Are you feeling up to answering some questions now? (*Bago tayo magsimula, nais ko lang siguraduhing komportable po kayo at handa nang sumagot ng mga katanungan. Handa na po ba kayo?*)

Research Instrument: Interview Questions

1. When you reflect on your experiences as a differently abled woman in your current setting, what specific events come to mind? What does your experience teach us about identity and resilience in a world that frequently ignores your point of view?

(Kapag iniisip mo ang mga karanasan mo bilang isang babaeng may kapansanan sa iyong kasalukuyang kalagayan, anong mga partikular na pangyayari ang pumapasok sa isip mo? Ano ang itinuturo ng iyong karanasan tungkol sa pagkakakilanlan at katatagan sa isang mundo na madalas na hindi pinapansin ang iyong pananaw?)

2. Reflect on your experiences as a differently abled woman during the job search process. What specific challenges or barriers have you encountered or observed? How have these obstacles influenced your ability to find employment? *(Balikan ang iyong mga karanasan sa proseso ng paghahanap ng trabaho bilang isang babae na may kapansanan. Ano ang mga espesipikong hamon o hadlang na iyong natagpuan o napansin? Paano nakaimpluwensya ang mga hadlang na ito sa iyong kakayahan na makahanap ng trabaho?)*
3. How do you anticipate differently abled women being involved in your field? Could you provide some particular situations or examples that illustrate how they are treated in terms of recognition and opportunities? *(Paano mo nakikita ang partisipasyon ng mga babaeng may kapansanan sa iyong larangan? Maaari ka bang magbigay ng ilang partikular na sitwasyon o halimbawa na nagpapakita kung paano sila tinatrato pagdating sa pagkilala at mga oportunidad?)*
4. Have you ever experienced being treated differently in social or professional situations due to a disability? Please share any personal stories or reflections where perceptions of disability may have influenced your job search or employment opportunities. *(Naranasan mo na bang tratuhin nang iba sa mga sosyal o propesyonal na sitwasyon dahil sa isang kapansanan? Mangyaring ibahagi ang anumang mga personal na kwento o pagninilay-nilay kung saan ang mga pananaw sa kapansanan ay maaaring nakaapekto sa iyong paghahanap ng trabaho o mga oportunidad sa trabaho.)*
5. Based on experiences, how do employers perceive the abilities and talents of differently-abled women in a corporate setting, according to what has been clearly communicated to you? Do these perceptions, as conveyed, align with reality, or do they appear to support existing biases? *(Batay sa iyong mga karanasan, paano tinitingnan ng mga employer ang kakayahan at talento ng mga kababaihang may kapansanan sa isang corporate na kapaligiran, ayon sa mga malinaw na naipahayag sa iyo? Ang mga pananaw na ito, na naipahayag, ay umaayon ba sa katotohanan, o tila sumusuporta lamang sa mga umiiral na pagkiling?)*
6. How have family, friends, mentors, or professional networks influenced your career progression or opportunities? *(Paano nakaimpluwensya ang pamilya, mga kaibigan, mga mentor, o mga propesyunal na network sa iyong pag-unlad sa karera o mga oportunidad?)*
7. How can employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations work together to create a more equitable and inclusive workplace environment where differently

abled women can thrive, free from barriers to employment and safety? (*Paano maaaring magtulungan ang mga employer, mga tagapagpatupad ng patakaran, at mga organisasyong nagtataguyod upang lumikha ng mas makatarungan at inklusibong kapaligiran sa lugar ng trabaho kung saan ang mga kababaihang may kapansanan ay maaaring umunlad, na walang hadlang sa trabaho at kaligtasan?*)

8. Reflecting on your current or past employment, in what ways has your workplace provided accommodations or support for your specific needs? (*Sa pagmuni-muni sa iyong kasalukuyang o nakaraang trabaho, paano nagbigay ang iyong lugar ng trabaho ng mga accommodation o suporta para sa iyong partikular na mga pangangailangan?*)
9. What advice would you offer to differently-abled women who are facing difficulties in their job search? Based on your experience, what strategies or mindset shifts would you suggest to help them succeed? (*Anong payo ang maibibigay mo sa mga babae na may kapansanan na nahihirapan sa kanilang paghahanap ng trabaho? Batay sa iyong karanasan, anong mga paraan o pagbabago sa pag-iisip ang iyong maipapayo upang matulungan silang magtagumpay?*)

Debriefing Questions:

1. **As we wrap up, what realizations have you had about this interview?** (*Ano-ano po ang mga napagtanto mo sa panayam na ito?*)
2. **Before we end, is there anything you'd like to share with us?** (*May gusto po ba kayong ipabahagi sa amin, bago po tayong mag tapos?*)
3. **What final insights come to your mind that you would like to leave us with?** (*Ano po ang mga huling pananaw na nais niyo po na maipahabagi samin?*)

Validation of the Instrument

The interview questionnaire was the most commonly utilized tool in research data collection to acquire significant information that was most reliable and suitably possible. Upon completing the interview guide questions, the researcher consulted their adviser first to check if the chosen questions were the studio.

For confirmation of the validity, the research instrument that the researchers used to obtain the results from the study, which aimed to determine "Accessibility for Dis-Ability: Empowering Differently Abled Women in the Labor Force," was validated by three (3) experts who had a background in research at the UPHSD Calamba Campus will then validate the research interview questionnaire. As identification, the validator had to be a graduate of a 4-year course with a background in research and a PRC license to ensure the reliability of findings through their expertise and methodological standards. Following that, the researcher received a certificate verifying their instrument.

Data Analysis

Narrative analysis sought to uncover meaningful life stories that people had to share, told in their own words and situations. Narrative analysis served as a data collection instrument and an interpretive framework for analysis in education, the social sciences, and health. It obtained the objectives by assisting people in understanding their health and well-being experiences within the context of their social environment, including narratives about themselves based on personal belief systems and self-perceptions (Ntinda, 2020).

After data collection, all interviews were transcribed verbatim and translated into English. The data were then grouped according to their attributes, and each group was labeled. Following the approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) for thematic analysis, the researcher systematically identified and explored the specific barriers faced by differently abled women. Patterns and prominent responses were examined to identify recurring themes. Subsequently, inferences were made from the data, and themes were generated to address the research questions.

Overall, the study "Accessibility for Dis-Ability: Empowering Differently Abled Women in the Labor Force" provided the foundation for advocacy campaigns and further research on these crucial issues. Giving differently able women a voice and making them the focus of this research aimed to create an inclusive environment where all people can engage fairly in employment relations.

Scope and Delimitations

This qualitative study had been conducted with women in the labor force in Calamba, Laguna. It was the most populous city in Region 4-A. Calamba had 539,671 people as of the 2020 census, accounting for 15.96% of Laguna's total population and 3.33% of CALABARZON's. The researchers chose Calamba because it was ideal for community-based research goals. By researching Calamba, researchers could get significant insights into the unique issues that differently abled women confronted in their community.

Semi-structured interview questionnaires were used to obtain the data during the first semester of the 2024 academic year. Five (5) differently abled women participated. Purposive and snowball sampling were used in the study to guarantee its validity. This method picked people according to predetermined criteria, linked participants who were far away, and confirmed the participants' direct knowledge of the specific issues faced by differently abled women.

RESULTS

Presentation

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Figure 1 displays the research paradigm used in conducting this study. The researchers would utilize semi-structured interview questions to collect data for their study on empowering differently abled women in the workforce—narrative analysis will be the qualitative method of data analysis for this research. The themes from the collected data were finally analyzed, and outcomes were shown.

According to Barkhuizen and Consoli (2021), narrative research was attractive to researchers who preferred qualitative approaches based on constructivism, which aimed at understanding what individuals had gone through from their perspectives. Though experience-centered inquiry includes a broader range of stories and resources to provide a complete view of participants' experiences, event-focused narrative research concentrates on specific events and the interpretations of people narrating them. This contrast highlighted how adaptable narrative approaches allowed for deep investigations

of individual occurrences and wide-ranging studies of lived experiences in various media and contexts.

Figure 2. Emerging Themes

Figure 2 shows the emerging themes identified during the qualitative data analysis. The central focus, the bullseye, symbolizes the ultimate goal: Empowering Differently Abled Women. This empowerment is achieved by navigating a complex interplay of factors, visualized as the arrows aiming for the target. The arrows themselves represent three key thematic areas: Barriers in Employment (the obstacles that must be overcome), Empowerment Through Holistic Support (the necessary resources and strategies for overcoming those barriers), and Building a Culture of Inclusive Practices (the long-term societal and workplace changes required for sustainable inclusion).

The Barriers in Employment arrow highlights the challenges faced by differently abled women, such as inequity, limited opportunities, stigma, ignorance, and workplace invalidation. These barriers act as forces pushing against the target, making it harder to achieve empowerment. This aligns with the participants' experiences of being misunderstood, undervalued, and facing systemic disadvantages.

The Empowerment Through Holistic Support arrow represents the strategies and resources that enable differently abled women to overcome these barriers. This includes community support, workplace accommodations, financial assistance, emotional support, and the development of resilience through faith, spirituality, and positive thinking. This arrow directly counters the force of the "Barriers" arrow, pushing towards the central goal of empowerment.

Finally, the Building a Culture of Inclusive Practices arrow represents the societal and workplace changes necessary for long-term, sustainable inclusion. This includes promoting equity, fair treatment, recognition of abilities, collaboration, and learning. This arrow aims to create a more welcoming and accessible environment, making it easier for differently abled women to thrive in the labor force. It represents the creation of a system where the "Barriers" arrow has less force, and the "Empowerment" goal is more readily attainable.

The image effectively conveys that empowering differently abled women requires a multi-pronged approach. It's not simply about addressing individual challenges or providing support in isolation. It requires a systemic shift towards inclusive practices that dismantle barriers and foster a culture where differently abled women are valued, respected, and empowered to participate fully in the workforce. This visual representation reinforces the study's findings and emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts from employers, policymakers, advocacy organizations, and communities to create a more equitable and inclusive society. The alignment with the De Luna-Narido and Tacadao (2021) study further strengthens the argument for addressing systemic challenges and promoting equitable opportunities.

Analysis and Interpretation

Research Question 1. What particular barriers to access do differently abled women faced in the workplace?

Central Theme A: Barriers in Employment			
SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES	EXCERPTS
1.1 Inequity	Instances of prejudice on disability status.	<i>Discrimination</i>	P1: “Merong discrimination sa mga katulad namin kasi may disability nga daw.”
		<i>Misunderstanding</i>	P3:” Yung unang naiisip ko talaga dati ay kung tatanggapin ba ako sa trabahong ito dahil nga ako may kapansanan”
		<i>Disadvantage</i>	P4: “Mahirap po maghanap ng trabaho. Pag nakita nila na PWD yun, matik, ignore ka nila “

1.2 Holistic Issues	Institutional challenges such as medical requirements or societal biases.	<p><i>“Medical Ailments”</i></p> <p><i>“Systemic Issues”</i></p> <p><i>“Applications that were disregarded”</i></p>	<p>P4: Ano, yun nga po mahirap po maghanap ng trabaho. Especially yung mga requirements, yung medical, mahirap po makapasa. Then pag nakita nila na PWD yun, matik, ignore ka nila yung application mo.</p> <p>P5: I still recall giving my doctor a thorough explanation of my job title in order to get his approval.</p>
1.3 Limited Opportunities	Barriers in achieving social and professional equality due to disabilities.	<p><i>“Will not be accepted because of a disability”</i></p>	<p>P3: “Yung unang naiisip ko talaga dati ay kung tatanggapin ba ako sa trabahong ito dahil nga ako may kapansanan”</p>
1.4 Experiencing Ignorance or Invalidation	The desire for explanation is a gasp for their humanity, experience, and context to be acknowledged in addition to a request for acknowledgment	<p><i>“Dismissed”</i></p>	<p>P1: “Dapat uunawain nila kami.”</p>
1.5 Stigma and Misunderstanding	Misconceptions about their disabilities and health by employers or peers, leading to unfair treatment or judgements.	<p><i>“Misjudged capabilities”</i></p>	<p>P3: “Akala ng mga katrabaho ko na hindi PWD ay tinatamad lang ako pero hindi naging mahina lang talaga ang katawan ko”</p>

1.6 Difficulty in Job Applications	The Challenges in securing jobs due to biases against PWDs, often being ignored during the hiring process.	<i>"Not hired"</i> <i>"Overlooked"</i>	P3: "Sa dati kong inapplyan na trabaho ako ay hindi napansin at hindi na hire dahil nga PWD ako."
1.7 Perceived Biases	The challenges differently abled women face due to negative assumptions and prejudices about their abilities.	<i>"Skills not validated"</i> <i>"Weakness emphasized"</i> <i>"Suggestions ignored"</i>	P4: "Parang hindi po nakikita yung kakayahan ko, yung maibibigay ko sa work... parang, mas, inaano nila yung weakness mo, kasi, di ba, differently abled woman ka nga."

Table 1: Barriers of Employment

The first central theme, **Barriers in Employment**, delves into the systemic and societal obstacles that hinder differently abled women from accessing and succeeding in the workforce. **1.1 Inequity** is a prominent issue, where participants reported facing discrimination despite existing legal protections. Choi (2020) emphasizes that even in environments with safeguards, prejudice, and stereotypes about disability limit full workplace participation. This aligns with findings that biases often prevent differently abled women from being considered for promotions or opportunities, highlighting the need for more profound cultural change.

1.2 Holistic Issues further reveal systemic inequalities, such as strict medical requirements that disproportionately disadvantage differently abled women. Gonzales et al. (2021) argue that such institutional barriers hinder fair job access and career growth, underscoring the urgency for policy reforms to create more equitable hiring practices.

Moreover, **1.3 Limited Opportunities** stem from societal misconceptions, as Ariyanto (2024) notes that these biases significantly restrict employment access for people with disabilities. Participants shared that these limitations are compounded by **1.4 Experiencing Ignorance or Invalidation**, which affects their emotional well-being and professional growth. Romeo et al. (2020) highlight how being dismissed or undervalued undermines confidence and hinders development.

1.5 Stigma and Misunderstanding persist as significant barriers in workplaces, perpetuating negative stereotypes and misconceptions about the abilities of differently abled individuals. Chen & Zammit (2023) argue that these attitudes create an

unwelcoming environment, obstructing career advancement. Similarly, **1.6 Difficulty in Job Applications** reflects the biases embedded in hiring practices, as Gonzales et al. (2023) found that employers often overlook qualified candidates simply because of their disabilities.

Finally, **1.7 Perceived Biases** remain a significant challenge, as Stoep (2019) highlights that implicit biases continue to affect workplace treatment, even with efforts toward inclusivity. These barriers underscore the pressing need for systemic reforms, cultural shifts, and inclusive policies to ensure equal opportunities and empower differently abled women in the labor force.

Research Question 2: What support systems are available to assist differently abled women in overcoming these barriers and securing employment?

Central Theme B: Empowerment Through Holistic Support			
SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES	EXCERPTS
2.1 Involvement and Recognition of Abilities	Employers and colleagues recognize the capabilities of differently-abled women and encourage resilience despite their conditions.	<i>"Can handle challenges"</i> <i>"Fighting"</i>	P4: "Yung owner po ng Resto..., pinag-provide po kami ng fit to work po" P1: "Pag meron sa amin nagkaroon ng problema, tinutulungan namin."
2.2 Accessibility and Support Systemes	Focuses on the crucial role of available resources and infrastructure in facilitating the inclusion of differently abled women in the workforce.	<i>"Authority Figures"</i> <i>"Benefits such as SSS and PhilHealth"</i> <i>"Salary Increase"</i>	P4: "Sa iba po, may benefits, maayos yung pamamalakad, sana po ganun din dito." P1: "Pag meron po silang mga programa sinasabihin po agad kami ng barangay or kahit sa clinic."
2.3 Systemic Aspects	Organizational and societal structures that accommodate the unique needs of differently abled	<i>"Financial benefits"</i> <i>"Little assistance"</i> <i>"Flexible time"</i>	P1: "Siyempre, pag mayroon sa lugar namin na mga finacial benefits"

	women in the workforce.		P4: “Doon po sa past employment ko madami pong benefits”
2.4 Emotional Aspects	Felt valued and understood by their employers, who took their specific needs into account.	“ <i>They understand us</i> ”	P2: “Iniintindi nila kaming mga PWD”

Table 2. Empowerment Through Holistic Support

The second central theme, **Empowerment Through Holistic Support**, highlights the importance of systems that provide comprehensive assistance to differently abled women. **2.1 Involvement and Recognition of Abilities** stresses that employers should focus on their skills and potential rather than viewing disabilities as limitations. Bowleg et al. (2022) suggest that workplaces that actively support growth and participation empower these individuals, boosting their confidence and engagement in professional opportunities.

Moreover, **2.2 Accessibility and Support Systems** are vital for fostering inclusivity. Anand and Sevak (2017) emphasize that accessible environments and proper accommodations enable differently abled individuals to perform effectively. Transitioning to **2.3 Systemic Aspects**, mechanisms like flexible schedules, financial aid, and community programs are essential for overcoming barriers. Gonzales et al. (2021) note that strict policies and a lack of resources significantly limit employment opportunities for people with disabilities.

Finally, **2.4 Emotional Aspects** underline the role of emotional well-being in empowerment. Jiang et al. (2022) highlight that support from colleagues and supervisors helps differently abled women build resilience, navigate challenges, and stay engaged at work. Together, these elements foster a holistic and empowering workplace environment.

Research Question 3: What new strategies can employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations apply in order to make work environments easier and safer for differently abled women?

Central Theme C: Building a Culture of Inclusive Participation			
SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES	EXCERPTS

3.1 Perspectives in Inclusion	Highlights the participants' views on what constitutes a truly inclusive workplace, offering valuable insights for employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations.	<i>"Treated as normal"</i> <i>"Favorable Treatment"</i>	P2: "Okay naman ang treatment dito sa amin sa kabila ng kapansanan namin, parang tinitreat na rin sila na normal." P5: "My boss, subordinates, and colleagues know my condition, and I'm always given the first priority in my work schedules since they know that I need to be on a shift with less stress."
3.2 Collaboration and Learning	Collective effort and mutual assistance within their community or professional networks.	<i>"Helpful coworkers"</i> <i>"Learning together"</i> <i>"Helping each other"</i>	P1: "Nagkakaisa kami dito... Tulungan kami, tulungan." P4: "Yung mga co-workers is mababait naman po and they help me naman po sa mga bagay na kailangan ko pang matutunan."
3.3 Acceptance in the Workplace	Companies are open to hiring differently-abled women and providing them with equal opportunities to prove their skills and potential.	<i>"Open to hiring,"</i> <i>"Equal opportunities"</i>	P3: "May mga kumpanya na kasi ngayon na open na sila sa pag hire ng mga babae na may kapansanan at nakikita nila yung kakayahan at potensyal naming mga PWD."

Table 3. Building a Culture of Inclusive Practice

The final central theme, **building a Culture of Inclusive Practices**, emphasizes the need to establish a workplace culture where inclusivity and diversity are integral

components of organizational values. **3.1 Perspectives on Inclusion** reflect the participants' views on what constitutes a genuinely inclusive workplace, where individuals are treated as equals.

3.2 Collaboration and Learning further reinforce the significance of teamwork in promoting inclusion. Participants indicated that cooperative environments, where colleagues assist each other and learn together, are key to fostering a culture of inclusion. This is consistent with research by Anand and Sevak (2017), who found that inclusive workplaces provide accommodations and encourage mutual support and learning among colleagues, enhancing overall workplace dynamics and productivity.

The final sub-theme, **3.3 Acceptance in the Workplace**, is particularly significant as it signals a shift towards greater inclusivity in hiring practices. Companies open to hiring differently-abled women and providing them with equal opportunities are seen as leaders in promoting workplace diversity. This finding reflects the work of Ariyanto (2024), who discusses how companies that embrace inclusive hiring practices provide differently-abled individuals with a chance to demonstrate their skills and reach their professional potential. When companies create an environment where individuals are hired and treated based on their abilities rather than their disabilities, it leads to more significant opportunities and professional growth.

The emerging themes highlight the critical importance of addressing the barriers preventing differently-abled women from thriving in the Workplace and providing the holistic support needed to empower them. By fostering inclusive practices, recognizing abilities, and providing systemic support, workplaces can transform into environments where differently-abled women can fully participate and contribute. The research underscores the need for societal shifts, policy changes, and organizational commitment to breaking down the barriers of inequity, stigma, and bias, ultimately creating a culture that values diversity and inclusion.

Research Question 4: What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?

EMERGING THEMES	
Central A: Barriers in Employment	Sub Themes: Inequity, Limited Opportunities, Holistic Issues, Experiencing Ignorance or Invalidation, Stigma and Misunderstanding, Difficulty in Job Applications, and Perceived Biases
Central B: Empowerment Through Holistic Support	Sub Themes: Involvement and Recognition of Abilities, Accessibility and Support Systems, Systemic Aspects, Emotional Aspects.

Central C: Building A Culture of Inclusive Practices	Sub Themes: Perspectives in Inclusion, Collaboration and Learning, Acceptance in Workplace
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Table 4. Emerging Themes

Three main themes emerged from the research: Barriers in Employment, Empowerment Through Holistic Support, and Building a Culture of Inclusive Practices.

The first theme, **Barriers to Employment**, shows these women's difficulties. They often experience inequity, limited opportunities, and holistic issues like lack of accommodations and understanding. Many feel ignored or invalidated, face stigma and misunderstanding, and struggle with job applications due to inaccessible systems and perceived biases during the hiring process.

The second theme, **Empowerment Through Holistic Support**, focuses on ways to help differently abled women thrive. Recognizing and involving their abilities, providing accessibility and support systems, and addressing systemic aspects like inclusive policies are key. Emotional support is also essential, as it boosts their confidence and resilience.

The third theme, **building a Culture of Inclusive Practices**, emphasizes the need for workplaces to embrace inclusion, promote collaboration and learning, and foster acceptance. By creating environments that value diversity, employers can help differently abled women succeed and contribute meaningfully to the workforce.

In alignment with this, Ditkowsky (2023) highlights the unique barriers differently abled women face in the workforce, such as discrimination, inaccessible workplaces, and lack of accommodations. These challenges often result in limited job opportunities and economic insecurity, especially for women of color. The guide emphasizes systemic changes, including enforcing anti-discrimination laws, improving workplace accessibility, and addressing wage inequities. By fostering inclusion and providing holistic support, workplaces can empower disabled women to thrive.

Research Question 5: Based on the results of the study, what output may be proposed?

JEN Empowerment and Wellness Initiative for Differently Abled Women (JENEWIDAW)

<i>Area of Concern</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Strategies & Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Persons Involved</i>	<i>Source of Fund</i>	<i>Success Indicators</i>
<i>Limited Employment Opportunity</i>	To increase access to job	- Conduct career fairs specifically		NGOs, Local Government, HR	Government grants, NGOs, CSR funds	At least 50 differently abled women

ies for Differently Abled Women	opportunities for differently abled women	y for differently abled women - Partner with inclusive employers for hiring programs	6 months	Departments, Women Leaders		gain employment or internships
Lack of awareness about workplace inclusivity	To raise awareness among employers about the benefits of workplace inclusivity and accessibility	- Organize workshops for employers about disability inclusion - Develop accessible workplace templates for employers	3-6 months	Employers, Advocates, Local Experts, HR Consultants	Sponsorships, CSR initiatives	At least 20 companies commit to improving workplace accessibility and hiring differently abled women.
Insufficient skills training tailored for the differently abled	To enhance skills and confidence of differently abled women for job readiness	- Implement free vocational training tailored to different disabilities - Launch mentorship programs led by successful women	1 year	Trainers, Mentors, Women Advocacy Groups, Experts	International aid, Private funding	80% of participants complete training and 70% secure relevant employment or entrepreneurial opportunities.

Mental health challenges among differently abled women	To promote mental health and well-being among differently abled women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide free counseling services tailored to their needs - Conduct mental health awareness campaigns and stress management sessions 	1 year	Psychologists, Mental Health Advocates, Support Groups	Mental health grants, NGOs, Local government funding	90% of participants report improved mental well-being and increased self-confidence in their personal and professional lives.
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Table 5. JEN Empowerment and Wellness Initiative for Differently Abled Women (JENEWIDAW)

The interventions aim to address the challenges faced by differently abled women, focusing on employment opportunities, workplace inclusivity, skills training, and mental health. These efforts are designed to empower them to thrive in the labor force and improve their overall well-being. By focusing on these key areas, the initiatives aim to create a more inclusive and supportive environment for differently abled women.

First, increasing employment opportunities is a priority. Many differently abled women face barriers when looking for jobs, so specific programs like career fairs and partnerships with inclusive employers are proposed. These activities will help them find suitable jobs and highlight their potential to employers. Success will be measured by the number of participants who secure employment or internships.

Next, raising awareness among employers about inclusivity is crucial. Many workplaces lack understanding of how to accommodate and include differently abled individuals. Workshops and accessible workplace templates are suggested to educate employers and encourage them to create supportive environments. These efforts aim to help businesses embrace diversity while providing opportunities for differently abled women.

Lastly, mental health is an important concern. Differently abled women may face additional stress and challenges, so providing counseling services and mental health programs is essential. These services will help them manage stress, boost confidence,

and improve their well-being. The goal is for participants to feel supported mentally and emotionally, enabling them to succeed in both personal and professional areas.

In conclusion, these interventions aim to empower differently abled women by addressing key challenges they face in the workforce and their mental health. Through collaboration with various stakeholders, the programs hope to create lasting change, ensuring that differently abled women can thrive in inclusive and supportive environments.

DISCUSSION

1. The barriers to access that differently abled women face in the workplace.

Differently abled women face several barriers in the workplace that limit their access to opportunities and professional growth. One major challenge is the lack of equal chances due to their disabilities, which makes it harder for them to achieve social and professional equality. They also encounter institutional barriers, such as strict medical requirements, that further restrict their participation in the workforce. Many face ignorance and invalidation, struggling to have their experiences and contributions recognized. Stigma and misunderstandings about their abilities lead to unfair treatment and judgments from employers and coworkers.

During job applications, biases against persons with disabilities often result in being overlooked for positions. Even when employed, their skills are underestimated, and their efforts often go unacknowledged, preventing them from receiving the recognition they deserve. These barriers hinder differently-abled women from fully participating in and thriving in the workplace.

2. The support systems available to assist differently abled women in overcoming these barriers and securing employment.

Currently, several support systems are aimed at helping differently abled women overcome barriers and secure employment. One key aspect is recognizing their abilities and encouraging their contributions through fair and supportive workplace environments. Accessibility is also a focus, with some organizations providing community support, workplace accommodations, and ensuring a safe and secure environment. Systemic measures such as financial assistance and flexible work hours are available to address their unique needs. Additionally, emotional support plays a vital role, as it involves fostering empathy and understanding among employers and colleagues, ensuring that differently-abled women feel valued and their individual experiences are respected. These combined efforts aim to create a more inclusive and empowering space for differently-abled women in the workforce.

3. The new strategies employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations apply to make work environments easier and safer for differently abled women.

Employers, policymakers, and advocacy organizations can adopt several strategies to create more inclusive workplaces. First, they should focus on equity by developing policies ensuring fair employee treatment. Providing tailored workplace accommodations, such as accessible facilities and adaptive tools, can help meet the unique needs of differently-abled women. Second, it is essential to recognize their abilities and contributions. This means creating an environment where their skills and potential are valued and celebrated. Lastly, promoting collaboration and learning within the workplace is key. Employers can encourage teamwork and support among colleagues, helping to build a culture of inclusion and acceptance. Organizations can foster a workplace where differently-abled women feel empowered and supported by working together.

4. The emerging themes based on the gathered data.

Based on the gathered data, three central themes emerged, each with 2 to 4 related subthemes. These central themes include barriers to employment, empowerment through holistic support, and building a culture for inclusive participation. These themes have contributed to the study's more profound understanding of the experiences and needs of differently abled women in the workplace.

5. The proposed output is based on the results of the study.

The proposed output is a comprehensive program known as the JEN Empowerment and Wellness Initiative for Differently Abled Women (JENEWIDAW). This initiative focuses on several key areas to improve the lives of differently abled women. It includes job placement programs designed to connect them with inclusive employers, skills training to enhance their job readiness, and campaigns to raise awareness among employers about the importance of workplace inclusivity. Additionally, mental health support is integrated to help them cope with their challenges and build their confidence, ensuring they are ready for success in the workplace and beyond.

JENEWIDAW aims to create an environment where differently abled women can access better job opportunities and thrive in their careers. By improving their skills and mental health, the program aims to foster an empowering environment that helps them grow personally and professionally. Success will be measured by the number of women securing jobs, the level of inclusivity in workplaces, and the improvement in their mental well-being, with the overall aim of helping them become confident, capable contributors to the workforce.

Conclusions

1. Differently abled women find it very unacceptable in the workplace: discrimination, no equal opportunities are accorded to them, as well as prejudices. These are

barriers to their career mobility as well as the reproduction of structural violence or discrimination.

2. While there are limited resources to support employees with individual disabilities, including women, through access and community services, there is still a lot to be done to support these ladies. They should encompass the promotion of diversity, sensitivity, and relevance, as well as student aid/scholarships and outreach/support.
 3. However, for differently-abled women, equality, understanding, tractability, and support in the workplace are not a priority for employers or policymakers, as few organizations can be considered inclusive or safe for disabled women who need advocacy. This includes practicing non-discrimination, offering required adjustments, and promoting diversity and respect.
 4. Several themes can be derived from the data collected: the strength of differently-abled women, their continuing struggles at the workplace, their wish to be recognized, their discrimination, and issues of accessibility and provisions they require. These themes give you an understanding of what they need and what they go through.
 5. Therefore, there is a need for strategies that assist differently abled women in the workplace, as shown by the study findings. These are making reasonable accommodations on the jobs, helping with the technologies they require, and cooperating with the organizations that advocate for them to have equal chances for achievements and promotions.
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Recommendations

The following recommendations guide various groups—differently-abled women, families, employers, policymakers, government, and researchers—toward building a more inclusive and empowering environment. These suggestions provide practical steps to support differently-abled women and foster understanding, inclusion, and growth.

1. **Differently-Abled Women.** Differently-abled women can take several proactive steps to overcome the barriers they face in the workplace. They need to engage with community support programs and advocacy groups to receive counseling, peer support, and access to resources tailored to their specific needs. Participating in skills training, entrepreneurship programs, and personal development courses will also allow them to gain autonomy, improve their employability, and secure better opportunities in the job market. Furthermore, developing self-advocacy skills is crucial in navigating workplace challenges, such as addressing biases and ensuring they receive necessary accommodations and recognition for their contributions. These efforts are necessary for enabling differently-abled women to thrive professionally and overcome the institutional and social barriers they encounter.
2. **Families.** Families are critical in supporting differently-abled women navigating personal and professional challenges. Families should engage in seminars, workshops, and support groups to better understand the unique obstacles these

women face. This will help them gain valuable insights into the barriers and opportunities available to differently-abled women in the workforce. By maintaining open communication, offering emotional support, and creating a cooperative and nurturing environment, families can help differently-abled women develop the confidence and resilience needed to succeed in their careers.

3. **Employers.** Employers must work towards creating inclusive, accessible, and supportive work environments for differently-abled women. One key recommendation is for employers to provide accommodations such as accessible workspaces, flexible work schedules, and adaptive tools. These accommodations ensure that differently-abled women can perform to the best of their abilities and have equal access to professional growth opportunities. Employers should also focus on fostering a work culture that values inclusion by conducting sensitivity training and promoting empathy, which helps to reduce biases and build better collaboration and productivity. Moreover, offering opportunities for career advancement and recognizing the contributions of differently-abled women ensures they are treated equally in the workplace, further empowering them to succeed.
4. **Policymakers.** Policymakers must enact and enforce laws guarantee accessibility, safety, and inclusivity in the workplace for differently-abled women. Legislation should be designed to ensure that workplaces are physically accessible and that women with disabilities are protected from discrimination. Furthermore, policymakers should advocate for systemic changes by fostering community-based programs that offer financial assistance, job training, and legal protections. These initiatives can create an environment where differently-abled women can pursue meaningful careers without facing unnecessary barriers. Additionally, implementing financial support structures will help provide the security and resources necessary for differently-abled women to participate fully in the workforce.
5. **Government.** The government is vital in ensuring workplaces are accessible and supportive of differently-abled women. Government efforts should promote public policies prioritizing inclusion and support for differently-abled women in the labor force. This can include incentivizing businesses to implement inclusive hiring practices and ensuring that public institutions lead by example in creating accessible environments. Increasing funding for programs that provide job training, financial assistance, and legal protections will also help alleviate the economic challenges that differently-abled women face. Additionally, the government should ensure that anti-discrimination and equal opportunity laws are effectively enforced so that differently-abled women are not excluded from career opportunities due to their disabilities.
6. **Future Researchers.** Future researchers should focus on investigating the intersectionality of disability and gender in the workforce, which can provide deeper insights into the unique challenges differently-abled women face in comparison to

their male counterparts or non-disabled women. By studying how these factors intersect, researchers can help shape targeted policies and strategies to address the specific needs of differently-abled women in the workplace. Furthermore, research into the long-term impact of community-based support programs and workplace accommodations is vital. Understanding how these support structures affect the career trajectory, mental health, and overall well-being of differently-abled women will provide essential data for creating more effective workplace policies. Finally, examining different strategies for workplace inclusion, such as adaptive technologies, flexible schedules, and inclusivity training, will help identify which interventions work best to ensure differently-abled women are employed and thrive in their professional roles.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers recognized the sensitive nature of the data they had gathered in light of the participants' varied backgrounds. They adhered to the Code of Ethics of the Philippine Psychological Association about confidentiality, which can be accessed for free on their website. Prior informed consent was acquired to protect the welfare and rights of the participants. This gave details on the study's objectives, potential advantages and disadvantages, and participants' freedom to quit the research at any time. To sum it up, researchers are guaranteed to maintain confidentiality and treat whatever information they collect for this study honestly and carefully.

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